

IMPACT OF EBULLIENT SUPERVISION AND GREEN HRM PRACTICES ON INNOVATIVE WORK BEHAVIOR: A MEDIATION-MODERATION ANALYSIS IN PAKISTAN'S HOSPITALITY SECTOR

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to find out the impact of Ebullient supervision (ES) and Green Human Resource Management practices (GHRM) on Innovative work behavior (IWB) of hospitality industry employees of Pakistan. Thus, staff innovation is a critical trait of an employee in today's hospitality sector to ensure that service quality, sustainability and competitiveness can be accepted in the organization. The study also introduces the Componential Theory of Creativity, in order to examine the psychological safety (PS) as mediator and the sense of belongingness (SOB) as moderator. The study was done through quantitative approach with explanatory technique and data was collected from 391 employee of the hotel industry in Pakistan. The analysis of the data was carried out using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method (Smart PLS, version 4 and SPSS). The results show that ebullient supervision and Green HRM Practices has significant positive effect on the psychological safety and innovative work behavior. Psychological safety is a great mediator between ebullient supervision and green HRM practices and innovative work behavior. In addition, sense of belongingness in a positive way is a moderator on the relationship between psychological safety and innovative work behavior. The research contributes to the literature on leadership, Green HRM and innovation in an integrated mediation-moderation model in a non-Western hospitality context. Results also offer empirical implications for hospitality managers who are looking for ways to foster innovation through supporting supervision practices, sustainable HR management, psychological safety and inclusion-focused relationships at work.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the current knowledge economy, being innovative is a requirement factor for the knowledge systems to sustain, adapt or survive (Damanpour & Aravind, 2012; Anderson et al.,

2014). In service industries, especially in the hospitality sector, innovation can be product or technology innovation, but also encompasses the daily work of employees, such as finding, promoting and implementing new ideas that can

facilitate the improvement of the customer experience, the operational efficiency, and the environmental fulfillment (Scott & Bruce, 1994; Janssen, 2000; Li et al., 2023). However, innovation in work behavior is put forward as one of the most important employability skills at the employee level that are necessary for the organization to meet changing customer preferences, technological development and impact of sustainability (Orth & Volmer, 2017; Kwon & Kim, 2020 and Ali et al., 2022).

In the hotel business, the service aspect depends on human interaction or service quality, which is very important for success of the hospitalization industry, increasing the quality of the experience and employee creativity to improve the experience. As one of the operational and effectiveness of the organization, employee ingenuity becomes noticeable in “in charge” when dealing with crowds in hotel and restaurants who often complain and disrespectful (Li & Peng, 2022; Oh & Jang, 2023). Despite several challenges such as the revolving door staff, hierarchical structure in management, inadequate level of training, job insecurity and unwillingness to change (Khan et al., 2020; Awan et al., 2024; Rasheed et al., 2024), the hospitality sector in Pakistan is expanding. These issues restrain the staff action in enhancing the services and innovative problem solving.

Green HRM is now an important strategic instrument to influence employee behavior which is related to the push for sustainability (Renwick et al., 2013; Jabbour & de Sousa Jabbour, 2016; Cherian et al., 2022). Green HRM is where environmental goals are included in recruitment, training, performance appraisal, rewards and employee involvement practices (Jabbour, 2011; Renwick et al., 2013; Khan et al., 2025). The previous studies have revealed that green HRM practices are positive influences on pro-environmental behavior, employee engagement, green creativity and green innovation (Moin et al., 2021; Afridi et al., 2023; Zafar, 2023). But despite these, the impact of Green HRM on the overall innovative work behavior, particularly in the Pakistani Hotel Industry is still under explored (Saghar, 2024; Rasheed et al., 2024).

Besides HRM practices, another important aspect influencing the psychological climate and motivational attitude towards innovation is the supervisory behavior (Amabile, 1996; Amabile and Pratt, 2016). A positive and energetic style of supervision that is characterized by enthusiasm with emotional support as a result which fosters a dynamic and motivating work environment referred to as Ebullient Supervision (Mashkoo & Muhammad, 2024; Ford et al., 2019). This supervision can have an even stronger impact on staff working in the hospitality industry where they are under stress and pressure from customers.

Psychological safety has been found to be the most critical psychological foundation to employee voice, learning, experimentation and innovation (Edmondson, 1999; Carmeli et al, 2009; Frazier et al, 2017). Allowing associates to take interpersonal risks and think outside the box (without being embarrassed, disciplined, or rejected) will increase their likelihood to share innovative ideas with others (Edmondson & Lei, 2014). Another important social and emotional consideration is a sense of belongingness, which is likely to further reinforce innovation-related behavior as those who feel valued and accepted are more likely to be committed and contribute new ideas (Baumeister & Leary, 1995; Shao et al., 2022; Shahid & Muchiri, 2019).

As such, this study aims to fill the theoretical and empirical gap by revealing the effects of ebullient supervision and Green HRM practices on innovative work behavior mediated by the psychological safety and testing the moderating effect of sense of belongingness. The study contributes to Componential Theory of Creativity which suggests that leadership and sustainable HRM, psychological safety and belongingness influence the employee innovation in the Hospitality sector of Pakistan (Amabile, 1996; Amabile & Pratt, 2016).

2. Theoretical Framework

This study is based on the Componential Theory of Creative which is the theory stated that the employee who possesses a relevant knowledge and is intrinsically motivated by the intrinsic potential to have the innovative behavior, while the

environment social where he or she is in is supportive (Amabile, 1996; Amabile & Pratt, 2016). In this article, these practices, namely ebullient supervision, and Green HRM practices are among the key organizational and managerial antecedents which serve as facilitators to improve employees' innovative work behaviors. Emotions in supervision are characterized by emotional energy, encouragement and positive supervision and support in employee's behavior to move towards innovation; Green HRM practices is characterized by providing policies, training, appraisal and reward system that ensure employee's behavior is directed towards innovation towards sustainability.

The mediating mechanism of the model is psychologically safe. Represents the transition of the enthusiastic supervision along with green HRM practices to innovative work behaviour. Supervisory support and HRM systems relate to employees' willingness to experiment with new work methods, engage in interpersonal risk, share new ideas and feel comfortable doing so

(Edmondson, 1999; Frazier et al., 2017). The above means that psychological safeness is a connection-specific relationship between independent variables and innovative work behavior.

We identified three mediators on the path linking psychological safe to innovative work behavior: sense of belongingness. The more employees feel they are accepted and respected, the more likely they will use their sense of psychological safety to contribute constructively, as that feeling of safety is directly tied to feelings of belongingness both inside and outside of the organization (Baumeister & Leary 1995; Shao et al. 2022). Hence, it is safe to assume that the influence of psychological safety on innovative work behavior is greater if the sense of belongingness of employees is higher.

Overall, the framework suggests that ebullient supervision and Green HRM directly and indirectly impact on innovative work behaviors; the relationship between psychological safety and innovative work behavior is enhanced by sense of belongingness

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework of the Study

3. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

3.1 Componential Theory of Creativity

This study is oriented on the Componential Theory of Creativity. The key elements in the theory are that creativity and innovation are a unifying force of domain relevant skills, skills of the creative process, intrinsic motivation toward the task and the work environment (Amabile, 1996; Amabile & Pratt, 2016). Skills in the domain are: Knowledge, Technical skills and experiences, and Processes in Creativity are:

Cognitively flexible, Capacity to take risks, and Capacity to generate new ideas (Shalley & Zhou, 2008). When it comes to creativity, if people feel intrinsically motivated, they can engage and focus on the creative work as the work is interesting or meaningful (Ryan & Deci, 2020; Tierney & Farmer, 2002).

The theory is very relevant in the current study since the implementation of Green HRM practices might impact how knowledgeable and motivated the employees are about being sustainable in the workplace, while ebullient

supervision might have an influence on providing emotional encouragement and positive energy (Renwick et al., 2013; Mashkooor & Muhammad, 2024). Psychological safety may foster a good social climate, enabling workers to express themselves and feeling of belonging may lead to emotional ties with their employer (Edmondson, 1999; Baumeister & Leary, 1995). In this way the Componential Theory of Creativity became an adequate conceptual framework to consider the influence of organizational and psychological factors on innovative work behavior.

3.2 Ebullient Supervision and Innovative Work Behavior

Ebullient supervision is characterized as the expression of enthusiasm, positive emotion, supportive interactions, encouragement and motivational energy of supervisory person (Ford et al., 2019; Mashkooor, J. & Muhammad, J., 2024). This ebullient type of behavior from a supervisor provides a favorable and stimulating work environment characterized by praise, celebration and open communication. These supervisors can influence the behavior of their employees via this, emotional contagion, building of trust and motivation, respectively (Bono & Ilies, 2006; Cameron et al., 2003).

Ebullient supervision is important in the hospitality industry as staff members have a high frequency of contact with customers, face pressure for time and have to be highly emotionally invested in the job. Positive and encouraging supervisors can help lower employee stress levels and improve employee engagement in innovative service enhancements. Previous studies have shown that positive supervisor behaviors related to positive employees' outcomes, such as engagement, job satisfaction, organizational citizenship behavior, and creative performance (Luthans & Avolio, 2009; Ford et al., 2019). Therefore, employees under the span of management under ebullient style of supervision is likely to be more pro-active and take actions on how to make use of the opportunity to create new ideas.

H1: Ebullient Supervision positively and significantly affects the employees' innovative work behavior.

3.3 Green Human Resource Management Practices and Innovation in work behavior

Green HRM involves HR practices which are environmentally sustainable and omitting ecological objectives to HR systems (Jabbour, 2011; Renwick et al., 2013; Jabbour & de Sousa Jabbour, 2016). All these practices mean green recruitment and selection, green training and development, green performance appraisal, employee program participation and green rewards. Green HRM can be utilized to train employee's mind and share the knowledge and motivate them to participate in green innovation (Kim et al., 2019; Cherian et al., 2022).

The results of previous studies indicate that Green HRM is pointed towards pro-environmental behavior, green creativity, and green innovative work behavior (Moin et al., 2021; Ullah et al., 2021 and Zafar, 2023). In the hospitality sector, Green HRM can stimulate their staff to come up with ideas for saving waste, energy conservation, green services for guests, and green hospitality operations (Butt et al., 2020; Gössling & Higham, 2022). However, taking the factors into consideration, Green HRM can become a catalyst for fostering innovative work behavior amongst the employees in Pakistan, as the awareness is limited in the country and in the hospitality organizations, they are facing numerous challenges both at environmental and quality aspects (Afridi et al., 2023; Rasheed et al., 2024).

H2: Positive and significant effect of green HRM practices on innovative work behavior of employees would be appreciated.

3.4 Green HRM Practices and Psychological Safety and Ebullient Supervision

Psychological safety is employers' confidence to voice their opinion, ask questions, make mistakes and propose new ideas without suffering negative consequences (Edmondson, 1999; Frazier et al., 2017). One of the most important parts of giving people psychological safety is through their supervisor, whose behavior and response is at the

front line of their evaluation of workspace safety (Edmondson & Lei, 2014).

The psychological climate of supervisors who have a positive mood is their positiveness, encouragement, empathy and openness. Supervisors' recognition of employees' contributions and positive feedback for employee ideas allows employees to feel confident about taking interpersonal risks (Carmeli et al., 2009; Ford et al., 2019). Green HRM practices might also help in creating a values-based climates in the organization, which can help in psychological safety (Renwick et al., 2013; Mahmood et al., 2023). If employees feel that the company cares about sustainability and moral values, as well as about upskilling, they could feel their respect and security valued by the company. Ebullient supervision positively and significantly affects the psychological safety.

H4: Green HRM practices have positive and significant impact on psychological safety.

3.5 Psychological Safety and Innovative work behavior

In terms of the innovative work behavior, employees need to question, propose, set up new ways to operate, and even to try new options and don't be afraid of failing (Scott & Bruce, 1994; Janssen, 2000). Psychological safety is thus critical as employees are unlikely to innovate if they feel that they will be "embarrassed" or "punished" for their innovative ideas (Edmondson, 1999; Frazier et al., 2017).

Previous research suggest that psychological safety can have positive effects among employees on learning (Carmeli et al., 2009), on voice (Edmondson & Lei, 2014), on creativity and on innovation (Cheng et al., 2020). When it comes to service, safe employees in service organizations are more likely to offer ideas on how to enhance customer service and operational processes. It can thus be concluded that the psychological safety has a strong, positive and influence on innovative working behavior.

H5: There exist positive and significant relationships between psychological safety and employees' innovative work behavior.

3.6 Mediating role of psychological safety

This can be attributed to psychological safety since ebullient supervision and Green HRM practices are psychological safety. The Componential Theory of Creativity (Amabile & Pratt, 2016; Amabile, 1996) suggests a supportive work environment is crucial in translating knowledge and motivation into creativity. The ebullient supervision would be the emotion support and motivation energy, and the Green HRM would be the Sustainability related resources and values (Renwick et al., 2013; Ford et al., 2019). Their natural, intrinsic talents, however, can only be converted to innovation when the employees feel psychologically safe (Edmondson, 1999; Frazier, et al., 2017).

Prior studies have shown that psychological safety has emerged as an important link between leadership and HRM practices and voice (Carmeli et al., 2009; Cheng et al., 2020), creativity and innovation. Hence, it is assumed that psychological safety will serve as a mediator between ebullient supervision and Green HRM practices' effect on the innovative work behavior.

The mediation test is as follows:H6: Psychological safety acts as a mediator between the variable of ebullient supervision and innovative work behavior.

H7: Psychological safety will be positively affecting to innovative work behavior because of Green HRM practices.

3.7 As a Moderator, Sense of Belongingness

Sense of belongingness is defined as when employees feel accepted, respected, valued and socially connected in the organization (Baumeister & Leary, 1995; Allen & Kern, 2017). Among psychologists, belongingness is a basic need directly impacting on motivation, resilience, commitment, and performance (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Shao et al., 2022). Employment feelings of belongingness are their positive feelings about the enterprise goals and their inclination to go beyond their official job description (Shahid & Muchiri, 2019; Lee & Fraser, 2024).

Collectivist society such as Pakistan, emphasize membership over the others as the social associations and group identity contribute

significantly in shaping the behavior of individuals in the workplace (Hofstede, 1980; Tajfel & Turner, 1979). Psychological safety gets people to speak up: belongingness gets people to contribute to the organization. Thus, the impact of psychological safety on the innovative work behavior might be greater in the case of high levels of belongingness.

H8: Positive moderation of psychological safety by sense of belongingness.

4. Research Methodology

The type of research used in the study was quantitative research type done with the deductive approach and the approach used in the study was an explanatory approach in investigating whether there were relationships between the research variables in direct, indirect and moderated models. Surveys were chosen because they are suitable in testing the theoretical relationship in the organization's behavior and HRM studies. Besides it, the target group of the research was the employees of the hotels/restrooms keeping the focus on the Hotel and Restaurant Industry of Pakistan. When the data was collected 391 valid respondents were present.

The questionnaire was initially designed on the already existing scales in the studies. Ebullient supervision was evaluated using items that revealed optimistic vitality, enthusiasm, positive speaking to and encouragement (Ford et al., 2019). The level of implementation of green HRM

practices was measured through measuring the following subdimensions: green recruitment, green training, green salary and green performance appraisal (Jabbour, 2011; Renwick et al., 2013; Kim et al., 2019). Psychological safety was measured using items from Edmondson (1999) and Frazier et al. (2017) that tapped into employees' perceptions of risk in taking interpersonal actions and contributing ideas. The measure of sense of belongingness was based on employees' sense of being accepted, respected and connected to the organization (Baumeister, Leary, 1995, Allen, Kern, 2017). Innovative work behavior was measured in line with idea generation, idea promotion and idea implementation (Scott & Bruce, 1994; Janssen, 2000).

SPSS and Smart PLS 4 were used to analyses the data. Data were screened and descriptively analyzed by using SPSS and measurement and structural models were tested using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) via Smart PLS 4. Prediction oriented analysis, mediation, and moderation of data coupled with latent constructs were appropriate, which led to the selection of PLS-SEM (Hair et al., 2021; Sarstedt et al., 2021).

4.1 Sample Characteristics

The demographic profile of the respondents is presented below. The final dataset consisted of 391 respondents from Pakistan's hospitality sector.

Table 4.1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Variable	Category Code	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	1	204	52.174
Gender	2	187	47.826
Age	1	72	18.414
Age	2	90	23.018
Age	3	71	18.159
Age	4	84	21.483
Age	5	74	18.926
Qualification	1	148	37.852
Qualification	2	133	34.015
Qualification	3	110	28.133
Experience	1	134	34.271
Experience	2	126	32.225

Experience	3	131	33.504
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Table 4.1 presents the coded demographic profile of the 391 respondents. The frequency column shows the actual number of respondents falling into each category, while the percentage column explains the share of each group within the total sample. In terms of gender, category 1 includes 204 respondents, representing 52.2% of the sample, while category 2 includes 187 respondents, representing 47.8%. This difference is small, which means that the sample is reasonably balanced and is not dominated by one gender category. Such balance is useful because perceptions of psychological safety, belongingness, and innovative behavior may differ across gender groups, and a balanced profile helps reduce the risk of one-sided responses.

The age distribution also reflects a broad spread of respondents. Category 1 includes 72 respondents, or 18.4%; category 2 includes 90 respondents, or 23.0%; category 3 includes 71 respondents, or 18.2%; category 4 includes 84 respondents, or 21.5%; and category 5 includes 74 respondents, or 18.9%. The largest age group is category 2, but it does not dominate the sample because all other age categories are also adequately represented. This pattern indicates that the responses were drawn from employees at different life and career stages, which strengthens the usefulness of the analysis because workplace perceptions may vary with age, maturity, and job exposure.

5. Results

The measurement model was found to have satisfactory levels of reliability and validity. Values of Cronbach's alpha, rho_A and composite reliability were more than the recommended value

of 0.70, supporting the internal consistency reliability of the instruments. Average Variance Extracted values were higher than 0.50 suggesting evidence of convergent validity. HTMT values (Hair et al., 2021; Henseler & Chin, 2010) were used to prove the discriminant validity, while the Collinearity was checked through VIF values.

The results of the structural model revealed that the supervision style had a significant impact on the variables of innovative work behavior and psychological safety. Moreover, there was a significant relationship between both green and innovative work behavior and psychological safety. Of the positive psychological impact variables, having psychological safety stood out as most salient with regard to innovative work behavior. This not only further validates the argument that positive supervisor behavior fosters conditions to support innovation from employees (Amabile 1996; Edmondson 1999; Renwick et al. 2013), it also demonstrates the importance of supportive HRM practices as a component of this.

5.1 PLS-SEM Model Estimation

After descriptive analysis, the hypothesized model was estimated in Smart PLS. The PLS algorithm estimated the measurement and structural parameters, while bootstrapping assessed the stability and statistical significance of the coefficients. In the model, ES and GHRM were treated as exogenous predictors, PS was treated as both an endogenous construct and a mediator, SOB was treated as a direct predictor and moderator, and IWB was the final outcome variable.

Figure 5.1: PLS Algorithm Model

Figure 4.1 presents the PLS algorithm model, including the estimated path coefficients and the measurement structure of the latent constructs. The values shown on the structural paths represent the direction and strength of relationships among ES, GHRM, PS, SOB, and IWB. The positive coefficients indicate that

increases in the predictor constructs are associated with increases in the outcome constructs. The figure also shows the outer loading pattern for the observed indicators, which helps confirm that the retained items contribute meaningfully to their respective constructs.

Figure 5.2: Bootstrapping Model

Figure 5.2 presents the bootstrapping model. Bootstrapping is important because it tests the stability and statistical significance of the estimated paths by repeatedly resampling the data.

The t-statistics shown in the figure indicate whether the coefficients are strong enough to be considered statistically reliable. Higher t-values suggest that the relationship is unlikely to be the

result of sampling error. Therefore, this figure visually supports the hypothesis testing results presented later in the chapter.

Table 5.1. Construct Reliability and Convergent Validity

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Ebullient Supervision	0.915	0.931	0.627
Green HRM Practices	0.877	0.907	0.620
Innovative Work Behavior	0.938	0.953	0.803
Psychological Safety	0.899	0.925	0.713
Sense of Belongingness	0.832	0.878	0.591

Table 5.2. Structural Path Results

Relationship	Beta	p-value	Result
ES -> IWB	0.184	< .001	Supported
ES -> PS	0.429	< .001	Supported
GHRM -> IWB	0.120	.001	Supported
GHRM -> PS	0.370	< .001	Supported
PS -> IWB	0.603	< .001	Supported
SoB -> IWB	0.093	.008	Supported
SoB x PS -> IWB	0.077	.048	Supported

Table 5.3. Mediation Results

Indirect Relationship	Beta	p-value	Result
ES -> PS -> IWB	0.259	< .001	Supported
GHRM -> PS -> IWB	0.223	< .001	Supported

5.2 Mediating and moderating analysis

Results from the mediation revealed uniformity and point to the mediation effect of psychological safe between ebullient supervision and innovative work behavior. Psychological safety was also specifically a mediator of the relationship between Green HRM practices and innovative work behavior. These results align with previous studies that have shown that psychological safety is an important mechanism by which leaders and HRM practices facilitate voice, creativity, and innovation (Carmeli et al., 2009; Frazier et al., 2017; Cheng et al., 2020).

Moderation results showed that the dimension of sense of belongingness was the moderating variables that significantly influence the relationship between the psychological safety dimension and the innovative work behavior. This could support the notion that psychological safety

is likely to encourage innovative behavior when workers experience a sense of social acceptance and emotional connection in their relationship with organizations (Baumeister & Leary, 1995; Shao et al., 2022; Shahid & Muchiri, 2019).

6. Discussion

Based on the result acquired in this study, it can be said that the theoretical model this study proposes is well supported. Firstly, relationship between ebullient supervision and innovative work behavior, the innovative work behavior of the respondents improved due to ebullient supervision. This finding is consistent with literature that positive leadership and supervisor support is positively related to creativity, motivation, engagement and innovation (Bono & Ilies, 2006; Ford et al., 2019; Luthans & Avolio, 2009). Hospitality organizations have bosses that

have a zestful approach and, can certainly help employees overcome anxiety and worry by creating a positive and supportive work environment.

Secondly, Green HRM practices had a positive impact on innovative work behavior. This result confirms previous studies which indicated that Green HRM can play a role in the sustainability behavior of employees, their green creativity and innovation (Renwick et al., 2013; Kim et al., 2019; Cherian et al., 2022; Afridi et al., 2023). Within a hospitality organization, green HRM can encourage employees to think creatively and come up with suggestions for energy-saving, waste reduction, sustainable customers service and sustainable practices (Butt et al., 2020; Gössling & Higham, 2022).

Third, there was evidence that innovative work behavior is an important outcome of psychological safety. This finding confirms the thoughts that employees who are not afraid to share ideas and take interpersonal risks (Edmondson, 1999; Carmeli et al., 2009; Frazier et al., 2017), will tend to innovate. According to the literature, psychological safety is especially important for employee voice and innovation and in a hospital setting, it is the employee who is closest to the customer to see the issues in the service.

Lastly, sense of belongingness played a moderating role between psychological safety and innovative work behavior. The results of this study support the concept that the sense of belonging leads to the greater tendency of employees to remain culturally attached to the organisation (Baumeister & Leary, 1995; Allen & Kern, 2017; Shao et al., 2022). Potential implications for future research in a collectivist work environment culture in Pakistan can also be to investigate whether the workers' creativity and voice is more likely to emerge when they feel socially connected and esteemed by the organization.

7. Theoretical Contributions

This study has a couple of 'gifts' to offer literature. Firstly, it extends the Componential Theory of Creativity and introduces 4 other components: green HRM practices, ebullient supervision, psychological safety, and sense of belongingness; all in a single model (Amabile, 1996; Amabile & Pratt, 2016). Second, it contributes to literature on

leadership by exploring the link between ebullient supervision and psychological safety in the workplace and innovative work behavior (Ford et al., 2019; Mashkooor & Muhammad, 2024). Thirdly, it has implications in Green HRM literature as it shows that enacting of the Green HRM practices not only affect the Environmental behavior but also the innovative work behavior (Renwick et al., 2013; Khan et al., 2025). Finally, in line with research in the field of psychological safety, the research reveals that employees' experiences of innovation are mediated by the overall psychological climate in the organization, rather than its practices (Edmondson, 1999; Frazier et al., 2017). Finally, this study contributes to the literature on belongingness dimensions by revealing in the context of the collectivist culture of the hospitality sector, the psychological safety-innovation relationship is strengthened by belongingness (Baumeister & Leary, 1995; Shao et al., 2022).

8. Practical Implications

The study has several implications for HR managers and HR practitioners in the hospitality industry. Disability organizations should arrange tutors to be adept in articulating their emotions and sociality in a positive, enthusiastic and encouraging way. Secondly, there is need of adopting Green HRM Practices in terms of green Training, Green Rewards and Green Job participation to develop sustainable Innovation among the organizations. The third step for managers to take is to make things "psychological safe," establishing an environment of open communication, positive suggestions from employees, and treating mistakes as learning opportunities. Fourthly, the employees should be involved, appreciated, made to feel part of the team and pay them fairly. Finally, businesses in the hospitality industry must understand that employee innovation isn't just about company policies and programs, it's also about the emotional support, the psychological safety and the social bonds.

9. Limitations, and Future Research Directions

This study has some restrictions. Firstly, it was a cross-sectional study; causal inferences cannot be drawn. Longitudinal designs should be used in future studies to investigate the effect that leadership and HRM practices have on innovation over time. Second, the study has focused on a hospitality sector; this model can be tested in other sectors such as Healthcare, Educational, Tourism industry, Banking and in Manufacturing sectors. Thirdly, self-reported data was used which may heighten the risk of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003; Kock, 2015). In the future, researchers might be able to access this information from a variety of sources (supervisors and employees). Lastly, future studies could explore more mediators and moderators such as creative self-efficacy, employee engagement, perceived organizational support, green psychological climate and organizational commitment, and organizational culture. Lastly, it is possible to perform comparative study across culture which would test whether the proposed model works across other cultures, particularly the western culture.

10. Conclusion

In the context of the current research, the influence of two dimensions of supervisory style ebullient and green HRM on innovative work behavior in hotels in Pakistan was explored. Ebullient supervision and Green HRM practices were found to significantly impact the innovative work behaviors. Table 2 shows that psychological safety was indeed confirmed as an important mediator and that feeling "at home" strengthened the relationship between psychological safety and innovative work behavior. The study found that in the context of a hotel, a stimulating and supportive leadership style, and sustainable HRM practices, psychosocial safety and positive relationships in the workplace, are relevant factors that can stimulate staff to innovate. This study offers substantial theoretical and practical contributions for literature related to leadership and Green HRM, psychological safety, belongingness, and innovation.

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